

RESEARCH TEMPLATE CHART – ASIA, AMERICAS

ASIA-GLYPH (PHOENIX LION TRIBE ID, HORSE, THAI, DRAGON 1 2 3

+ WHOLE-ASIA CEMENT BAN-landed per), AMERICAS

RESEARCH TEMPLATE CHART – Rocket Design, ATM Design and Computer Chips: Doctor of
Computers / Rocket (Flight s/w) Thesis

<p>PHOENIX STAR LION TRIBE ID DOLLAR</p> <p>PHOENIX TEL (LION TRIBE ID) SIM CARD</p> <p>PHOENIX PASSPORT VISA</p>	<p>SEE: RESEARCH TEMPLATE ATTACHED</p> <p>CEMENT MIXER move-hide-in: ILLEGAL 'A' REFUGEES + CEMENT-MIXER FRAUD Legislative COUNTERFEIT theft + PASTE 'SINGA'- COUNTERFEIT buildings & UNI. + ALL X (ASIA_CN-X COUNTERFEIT MSIAN-'SINGA' HK-X NY-X ports rapists X500 SHOTS dg-X, SAT-TELCOM hide-in) + FACTORIES (auto-debarred 1. SPOILT LAND- ELECTROCUTION: BEHEAD 1925) = PER Y PER CRIME OP X 120 DEBT DUE (LAND-cannot count)</p>	<p>KEY ECONOMIES</p>
<p>PHOENIX ROCKET</p>		
<p>Phoenix Rocket</p>		
<p>Phoenix Tri-Solar Panels</p>		
<p>Phoenix Plasma</p>		
<p>Phoenix Cluster M</p>		
<p>Phoenix simulation 'take-out' (money + land WAR PRISON ID) part Tri-Solar Tech Trades PHOENIX DOLLARS</p>		
<p>PHOENIX CHIP</p>	<p>PHOENIX-SOUTH, HORSE-THAI, DRAGONS-CN J K</p> <p>(1) LION DOLLAR (HEAVEN EARTH BILLION Y) 3-IN-1 ATM PHOENIX SEAL (6-POINT STAR) TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES</p> <p>(2) HORSE DOLLAR ATM by PHOENIX ATM (DIFFUSION unto LANDED PER GLYPH)</p> <p>...</p> <p>(3) DRAGON 1: PHOENIX CHAO ZHOU BANK</p>	<p>KEY ECONOMIES</p> <p>TRI-SOLAR ATM = 1-CALSTATE 1-OTHER</p>
<p>Phoenix Chip Manufacturing</p>		

Semiconductor IC Integrated Circuit		
Phoenix AI (Laws)		
PHOENIX S/W		
Phoenix Programming		
WLC WAR PRISON DESIGNATE (NEW) JUDGES + PER ASIA STATE ARCHIVES	PER ASIA-GLYPH: LION TRIBE ID ZONE HORSE / THAI / DRAGON 1 2 3: CN STATE 1.SPOILT LAND-ELECTROCUTION 48H WAR PRISON (e.g. AUTO-BAR criminal paperwork AUTO-VOID) 2. Pre-med INFRA-genocide: Time-Related (Medi-Crime: BIO-W 'counterfeit-money') Repeat 3. INFRA-counterfeit THEFT 4. INFRA-COLLAPSE: Time-Related: REVERSE-COLLAPSE, REVERSE-Inject. TERMINATE: WAR PRISONERS SHIP-OFF COUNTERFEIT COUNT PROJECTED FUTURE = PHOENIX ATM CARD BANK (record PERP-ID AMT) PHOENIX GRANITE LANDED COMPULSORY LAW = WHOLE ASIA-GLYPH PER GLYPH HEAD	WAR PRISON LOCK-DOWN ID-INDIAN STATES give birth: 1. SPOILT LAND (> 120 UP 500) TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES SHIP-OFF: INDIA DROP-OFF
PHOENIX GRANITE LANDED contractors sign-up: 3-IN-A ATM PLUG-IN	PHOENIX GRANITE LANDED contractors sign-up promotion + HAN-SHENG JING (Painting Frames: YAH NAME OF SPACE-> BILLION Y GLYPH GOD): best catalogue (Tri-Solar Tech Trades) household items	
	RF-CLEAN PRACTICE: INDIAN TEMPLES ETC	TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES

TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (CORRECT): 1-SET (1-AREA): PFIZER STOCKPILE (TE-majulah-sek TRANSFER: LION TRIBE ID DOLLAR AUTHORITY) 0-indians AUTO-BAR 'law-less: 1. SPOILT LAND REPEAT CRIME: WAR PRISON 48H-ELECTROUCTION

TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES	PER Y Document Archive	STATUS: AUTO-BAR 48H-Hang	PFIZER BLOOD 1-SET: X500	Package Evidence Proof: 0 Indians	NEW FORMAT Change: TO NEW ASIA PLATFORM ALL ASIA-GLYPH STOCKLIST: Take-out
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Rajah Tan: ASIA CTY A-Z (WAR PRISON)	Y1 ... – Y X	AUTO-BAR (VOID) Assassinated by LOCAL ASIA MILITARY	ASIA Rapists: spawn (e.g. 'asean' + 1 2 3 Dragons + Beyond LION TRIBE ID (PHOENIX STAR) Continent	SENT: NYSE LSE	TRANSFER e.g. Tri-Solar Tech Trades (NEW) + Phoenix Granite Landed Estates (with Privacy Children's Playground: NO accidental mix-strangers, 0-Indians: 100% Wrong DNA) Diffusion (PLUG Horse ATM + Phoenix ChaoZhou ATM etc: Cash- out
Rajah Tan: ASIA (WAR PRISON)		AUTO-BAR (VOID) Assassinated by LOCAL ASIA MILITARY	Ports Rapists: X500	SENT: NYSE LSE	
Global (WAR PRISON) Indian Sch		AUTO-BAR (VOID) Assassinated by LOCAL ASIA MILITARY	Repeat Ports Rapists: X500	SENT: NYSE LSE	
Town Council + Clear Garbage: Mazar LLP Billing (Billing: MND 1- Indranee Rajah Tan (msia-refugee no bodMND		AUTO-BAR (VOID) Assassinated by LOCAL ASIA MILITARY	Repeat Ports Rapists: X500	SENT: NYSE LSE 0-indians	

**TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (CORRECT): 1-SET (1-AREA): PFIZER STOCKPILE (TE-majulah-sek
TRANSFER: LION TRIBE ID DOLLAR AUTHORITY) 'OFFICE'-A (WAR PRISON)**

TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES ('OFFICE')-A	PER Y Document Archive	STATUS: AUTO-BAR (WAR PRISON) 48H-Hang	PFIZER BLOOD 1-SET: X500	Package Evidence Proof: 0 Indians	NEW FORMAT Change: TO NEW ASIA PLATFORM ALL ASIA-GLYPH STOCKLIST: Take-out
THARMAN INDRANEE PUTHU X500 DG-X X500 INSOL-SHANMUGAN (PORTS RAPISTS X500) (WAR PRISON)	Y1 ... - Y X		Secretaries AUTO-BAR 'signatures' PER document: missy inject 4-5 shots Pfizer x 30 days	SENT: NYSE LSE	TRANSFER e.g. Tri-Solar Tech Trades (NEW)
BAN MEET ASIA CTY A-Z e.g. BALA (WAR PRISON) 100% Wrong DNA & Notes					
ASIA Rapists: spawn (e.g. 'asean' + 1 2 3 Dragons + Beyond LION TRIBE ID (PHOENIX STAR) Continent					

**TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (CORRECT): 1-SET (1-AREA): PFIZER STOCKPILE (TE-majulah-sek
 TRANSFER: LION TRIBE ID DOLLAR AUTHORITY) 'OFFICE'-B (WAR PRISON)**

TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES ('OFFICE')-B ILLEGAL 'A' (PFIZER BLOOD SAMPLES SET)	PER Y Document Archive	STATUS: AUTO-BAR (WAR PRISON) 48H-Hang	PFIZER BLOOD 1-SET: X500	Package Evidence Proof: 0 Indians	NEW FORMAT Change: TO NEW ASIA PLATFORM ALL ASIA-GLYPH STOCKLIST: Take-out
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<p>MAS (WAR PRISON)</p> <p>100% Wrong Notes: PASTE 'S' wrong</p>	<p>Y1 ... – Y X</p>	<p>AUTO-BAR 'signatures' PER document: 100+ ASIA+ = X120 DEBT DUE + 100+ Currencies DEBT DUE</p>	<p>Package Delivery inject 4- 5 shots Pfizer x 30 days: ALL DEPT include: 'legislative dept' 'law dept': like LLD Doctor of Law Paste 'War- Wick'= 48H- Hang: 0-indians</p>	<p>SENT: NYSE LSE</p>	<p>TRANSFER e.g. Tri-Solar Tech Trades (NEW)</p> <p>1. Spoilt Land 2. Genocide(s) 3. Repeat crime BEYOND PHOENIX: 0-indians 0-MAS=Pfizer Blood Samples</p>
<p>HDB, BCA-write nonsense no. (open 1. SPOILT LAND- ELECTROCUTION 48 H (WAR PRISON)</p>	<p>Y1 ... – Y X (NO ESTATE) + OVERSEAS COMBINED TOTAL ASSETS 1.SPOILT PHOENIX 2. REPEAT CRIME SPOILT ASIA CN from SPOILT PHOENIX</p>				<p>1. Spoilt Land 2. Genocide(s) 3. Repeat crime BEYOND PHOENIX: 0-indians 0-HDB, BCA, ALL ILLEGAL 'A' =Pfizer Blood Samples</p> <p>2. REPEAT CRIME SPOILT ASIA e.g. CN, spawn rajah-'dirty' + de- cement (RF-specialist) from SPOILT PHOENIX BEYOND: (Change PHOENIX ATM PLUG-IN: Cash Out + Chao Zhou ALL Landed Original Ancestry + Other states: _)</p>

**TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (CORRECT): 1-SET (1-AREA): PFIZER STOCKPILE (TE-majulah-sek
TRANSFER: LION TRIBE ID DOLLAR AUTHORITY) 'OFFICE'-C (WAR PRISON)**

<p>TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES ('OFFICE')-C</p>	<p>PER Y Document Archive</p>	<p>STATUS: AUTO-BAR (WAR PRISON) 48H-Hang</p>	<p>PFIZER BLOOD 1-SET: X500</p>	<p>Package Evidence Proof: 0 Indians</p>	<p>NEW FORMAT Change: TO NEW ASIA PLATFORM</p>
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<p>ILLEGAL 'A' (PFIZER BLOOD SAMPLES SET)</p>		<p>AUTO-BAR 'signatures' PER document: 100+ ASIA+ = X120 DEBT DUE + 100+ Currencies DEBT DUE</p>			<p>ALL ASIA-GLYPH STOCKLIST: Take-out</p>
<p>'Ministries'- CEMENT MIXER 1.SPOILT LAND (Check Y: move-in (WAR PRISON) 'singapura' Islanders passport different from: 'singaporeans'- msian family counterfeit 100% Wrong Notes: PASTE 'S' wrong</p>	<p>Y1 ... - Y X WAR PRISON FUNCTION: Counterfeit (100% Wrong Notes) Collection ONLY</p>	<p>+ NO Corresponding Matching AMT = Manufacturing Plant Weapons</p>	<p>Package Delivery inject 4-5 shots Pfizer x 30 days: ALL DEPT include: 'legislative dept' 'law dept': like LLD Doctor of Law Paste 'War-Wick'= 48H-Hang: 0- indians</p>	<p>SENT: NYSE LSE</p>	<p>1. RE-TAKE 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES from inside N <u>SHIFT-into BLKS MSIA:</u> (msian counterfeit b collect) 'singapura' Islanders passport different from: 'singaporeans'-msian family counterfeit (LION TRIBE ID-chinese islanders-FARMLAND + LANDED [BILLION Y CONTINENT] -destroyed 1. SPOILT LAND: cement mixer (check y: HDB BCA ETC): do not know MSIA/MSIAN) 2. TRANSFER: TOTAL 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES = LION TRIBE ID BANK n AUTHORITY (record)</p>
<p>GIC 'invest'ment</p>				<p>1-Y 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES: Suffice</p>	<p>1. RE-TAKE 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N</p>

<p>*Te-majulah-sek: VIP Access (NOT Counted)</p>				<p>American LAND PURCHASE + SATELLITE ROCKET LAUNCH + Tri-Solar Tech Trades (ATM PLUG)</p> <p>Others: Phoenix Granite Landed Contractors Sign-up: ATM Plug set-up (HORSE/CN/ASIA/USA 1,2-STATE) actual investment</p>	<p>SALARIES from inside N SHIFT-into BLKS MSIA: (msian counterfeit b collect)</p> <p>2. TRANSFER: TOTAL 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES = LION TRIBE ID BANK n AUTHORITY (record)</p> <p>3. Tri-Solar Tech Trades (NEW)</p>
<p>'Ministries'- 'S'-TAX TOTAL AMT (Various) CEMENT MIXER 1.SPOILT LAND (Check Y: move-in (WAR PRISON))</p> <p>100% Wrong Notes: PASTE 'S' wrong</p>	<p>Y1 ... - Y X</p> <p>WAR PRISON</p> <p>FUNCTION: Counterfeit (100% Wrong Notes) Collection ONLY</p>				<p>1. RE-TAKE 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES from inside N SHIFT-into BLKS MSIA: (msian counterfeit b collect)</p> <p>2. TRANSFER: TOTAL 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES = LION TRIBE ID BANK n AUTHORITY (record)</p>

TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (CORRECT): 1-SET (1-AREA): PFIZER STOCKPILE (TE-majulah-sek TRANSFER: LION TRIBE ID DOLLAR AUTHORITY) 'OFFICE'-D (WAR PRISON)

<p>TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES ('OFFICE')-D</p>	<p>PER Y Document Archive</p>	<p>STATUS: AUTO-BAR (WAR PRISON) 48H-Hang</p>	<p>PFIZER BLOOD 1-SET: X500</p>	<p>Package Evidence Proof: 0 Indians</p>	<p>NEW FORMAT Change: TO NEW ASIA PLATFORM</p>
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ILLEGAL 'A' (PFIZER BLOOD SAMPLES SET)		AUTO-BAR 'signatures' PER document: 100+ ASIA+ = X120 DEBT DUE + 100+ Currencies DEBT DUE			ALL ASIA-GLYPH STOCKLIST: Take-out
PASTE: NU-'S'-H- NTU-0 Rajaratnam, 0 Warwick, 0- Indians, Msian LKY SCH: 0 indians Jayakumar(s), Mahbubani etc	Y1 ... - Y X				1. RE-TAKE 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES from inside N SHIFT-into BLKS MSIA: (msian counterfeit b collect) 2. TRANSFER: TOTAL 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES = LION TRIBE ID BANK n AUTHORITY (record)
PASTE: S'- Pte sch	Y1 ... - Y X				
'Global' 0-Indians SCH (WAR PRISON)	Y1 ... - Y X				

**TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (CORRECT): 1-SET (1-AREA): PFIZER STOCKPILE (TE-majulah-sek
TRANSFER: LION TRIBE ID DOLLAR AUTHORITY) 'OFFICE'-E (WAR PRISON)**

TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES ('OFFICE')-E ILLEGAL 'A' (PFIZER BLOOD SAMPLES SET)	PER Y Document Archive	STATUS: AUTO-BAR (WAR PRISON) 48H-Hang AUTO-BAR 'signatures' PER document:	PFIZER BLOOD 1-SET: X500	Package Evidence Proof: 0 Indians	NEW FORMAT Change: TO NEW ASIA PLATFORM ALL ASIA-GLYPH STOCKLIST: Take-out
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		100+ ASIA+ = X120 DEBT DUE + 100+ Currencies DEBT DUE			
PASTE: FACTORIES + SUB-CONTRACT WORKERS (ODD – FRAUD Accountants) (stock list	Y1 ... – Y X	FACTORIES + Items + humans (all nationalities) = shift into RE- TAKE COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES from inside N SHIFT BACK- into BLKS MSIA + various: CN, TW HK (complete removal: OFF PREMISE nothing to steal: (odd-PFIZER-0 0-indians entry premise)			1. RE-TAKE 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES from inside N SHIFT-into BLKS MSIA: (msian counterfeit b collect) 2. TRANSFER: TOTAL 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES = LION TRIBE ID BANK n AUTHORITY (record) 3. PLUG PHOENIX CHAO ZHOU ATM: CASH-OUT HOMELAND(S) 3. NEW FORMAT Change: TO NEW ASIA PLATFORM ALL ASIA-GLYPH STOCKLIST: Take-out HORSE-ATM: IF phoenix granite landed contractors sign-up with privacy playground (0-indians) AFFORDABLE: based – occupier + high salaries not required.

					<p>4. TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (RF-CLEAN HOME intruders): GLYPH TRANSFER</p> <p>5. Predicted: PFIZER 0-Indians CLEAR INDICATION (1) Elimination: intense dislike TO WHITE SKIN: (2) AUTO-swiftly ditch own NYSE LSE + ditch 0-Indian (sch-kill per batch, Canada etc Japan etc) + request join GLYPH, pending approval. (3) NEW ASIA FORMAT: NO 1. SPOILT LAND 2. Genocide(s) REVERSED</p>
Town Council + Clear Garbage: Mazar LLP Billing (Billing: MND 1-Indranee Rajah Tan (msia-refugee no bodMND		AUTO-BAR (VOID) Assassinated by LOCAL ASIA MILITARY	Repeat Ports Rapists: X500	SENT: NYSE LSE 0-indians	

TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (CORRECT): 1-SET (1-AREA): PFIZER STOCKPILE (TE-majulah-sek TRANSFER: LION TRIBE ID DOLLAR AUTHORITY) 'RETAIL'-A & MOVIE ACTRESS (WAR PRISON)

<p>TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES</p> <p>('RETAIL')-A & MOVIE ACTRESS</p>	<p>PER Y</p> <p>Document Archive</p>	<p>STATUS: AUTO-BAR (WAR PRISON)</p> <p>48H-Hang</p> <p>AUTO-BAR 'signatures' PER document: 100+</p>	<p>PFIZER BLOOD 1-SET: X500</p>	<p>Package Evidence Proof: 0 Indians 0 Muslims</p>	<p>NEW FORMAT Change: TO NEW ASIA PLATFORM</p> <p>ALL ASIA-GLYPH STOCKLIST: Take-out</p>
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<p>ILLEGAL 'A' (PFIZER BLOOD SAMPLES SET)</p>		<p>ASIA+ = X120 DEBT DUE + 100+ Currencies DEBT DUE</p>			
<p>PASTE: ONLY ALERT ASIA BAN 0-INDIANS</p> <p>NOT HIGHLIGHT / PROMOTE: (1) NO TIME promote (CN = smelly cn msia singaporeans men woman 'attack' uni. =shift into MSIA FOR LARGE COUNTERFEIT- SALARIES ALURE)</p> <p>1. RET. NU- PASTE 'S' NTU-KEYS [PER Y PER CRIME OP]</p> <p>2. PLUG IN PHOENIX- HORSE, DRAGON ATM: shift out</p> <p>(2) ONLY SCREEN IMAGES: PACIFY TEMPORARILY +</p>	<p>Y1 ... - Y X</p>	<p>FACTORIES, RETAIL, MAS- PFIZER BLOOD SAMPLES (whole asia: gun power waiting outside building VIDEO 1-1 Arrest) : LV-Imperial LOGO</p> <p>0-indians entry premise 0-Muslims entry LION TRIBE premise (shift sch- muslim attacks: into MSIA)</p> <p>: electronics: Maybe -Imperial LOGO (IEEE springer hide: non- chargeable / written content more less same repeat old knowledge)</p> <p>(1) HAN-DNA NOT Found in 58 ETHIC mainland CN: only</p>			<p>1. RE-TAKE 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES from inside N SHIFT-into BLKS MSIA: (msian counterfeit b collect)</p> <p>2. TRANSFER: TOTAL 'LARGE' COUNTERFEIT N SALARIES = LION TRIBE ID BANK n AUTHORITY (record)</p> <p>3. PLUG PHOENIX CHAO ZHOU ATM: CASH-OUT HOMELAND(S)</p>

<p>CONTINUE TO 1. SPOILT LAND (ROB) 2. GENOCIDE(S) CLEAR INDICATION: PFIZER BLOOD SAMPLES - 'GLOBAL' 0- Indians = ASIA-CLEAN, PORTS Rapists-CLEAN (X500 SHOTS, X500 SUMS = LION TRIBE ID BANK N Various)</p>	<p>AUTHOR IS DA-WEI descendent (heaven earth name of chinese GOD: printed, CULT COPY chinese GOD'S name) TYPE + PHOENIX 6-STAR + 8-STAR + TRI-SOLAR</p> <p>AUTHOR IS: 20+-30early: 96% PERCENTILE Amongst WORLD's 1% PHD [Not world] EXAM USA Pre-law: 100% score 2018</p>	<p>coastal etc outside CN</p> <p>Meaning: (2) NOT DA-WEI descendent of LION TRIBE GLYPH TEXT (1-Example: NI-XI-BILLION Y CONTINENT)</p> <p>(3) paste 'WANG' OBVIOUS INDICIATION: fraudsters 1. SPOILT LAND 2. Genocide(s) Paste: wrong 'law'-war wick + Paste 'WANG' attack correct 'law' 2008 – 1. SPOILT LAND e.g. CN 2. Genocide(s) = so no time promote self-gain 'CN' individuals-self-interested Maharani-attack 'economists'-NTU Indo-WCS=SCAM-indranee, thiru (Indians)</p>			
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		<p>AUTO-VOID = 1. SPOILT LAND- ELECTROCUTION 48H) AUTO-BAR: rajah (ESC TO: MSIA) criminal 'LAW- LESS' practice [whole island: AUTO-BAR HANG] paperwork worth \$0 + NO ESTATE</p> <p>1. SPOILT LAND- ELECTROCUTION 48H) spawn outlets: ASSASSINATED BY LOCAL MILITARY</p>			
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RESEARCH OUTCOME:

PHOENIX LION TRIBE \$	HORSE \$	DRAGON 1: CHAO ZHOU	DRAGON 2: JP	DRAGON 3: K	TIGER USA \$ 1-2 STATES CANADA	COLLECTION COMMITTEE: 1905 Hong Leong DBS-CEMENT MIXER-posb 1925 SPOILT LAND TO 2025 REPEAT SPOILT LAND + INFRA-genocide + BEYOND	FRAUDSTERS CEMENT MIXER REFUGEES MOVE-IN FRAUD OFFICE LEGISLATIVE COUNTERFEIT B THEFT (WB-WT pre-med 1985 spawn x 3) + MALLS + OVERSEAS ASSETS FROM SPOILT PHOENIX = RET. KEYS + X 120 DEBT DUE
PHOENIX GRANITE LANDED +	LANDED	LANDED	LANDED	LANDED	PHOENIX GRANITE LANDED	PHOENIX CONTRACTORS SIGN-UP: KEY STATES	RF-CLEAN RUPEE BLK NO. 1 + HDB BCA OFFICE + ILLEGAL 'A' +

LION ISLAND PHOENIX TELCOM							
PHOENIX LION TRIBE ATM					TRI- SOLAR ATM	LOGISTICS PLUG IN	ALL COUNTERFEIT 'SG'-X + X ITEMS=ALL TELCOM SATCOM + ST- ELECTRONICS
TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (GLYPH INVENTORS)	TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (GLYPH INVENTORS)	TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (GLYPH INVENTORS)	TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (GLYPH INVENTORS)	TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (GLYPH INVENTORS)	TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES (GLYPH INVENTORS)		ALL COUNTERFEIT 'SINGA' UNI.=RET. KEYS PER Y OP + PER CRIME SUFFICE: to SET-UP ROCKETS SYSTEMS KEY STATES

EXAMPLE 1: [NEW KLL\$ With Pool Estate diffusion OP: by Phoenix-Lion Tribe ID ATM designer HORSE DOLLARS]

EXAMPLE 2: BASIC LANDED JOHOR PLUG-IN Phoenix-Lion Tribe ID ATM designer HORSE DOLLARS]
+ METAL CARS PARKING IN-HOUSE

(DIFFUSION HDB FRAUD STACKED HUMANS, BCA FRAUD SPOILT-LAND-ELECTROCUTION LISTED, X120 DEBT PER DB-CEMENT MIXER + INFRA-GENOCIDE + INFRA- THEFT COUNTERFEIT 'SINGA' + INFRA- CEMENT SPOILT LAND-ELECTROCUTION + INFRA-REPEAT SPOILT LAND BEYOND PHOENIX + HORSE + THAI + DRAGON 1 2 3 + WHOLE ASIA (Rajaratnam COUNTERFEIT REFUGEES 'SINGA' UNI. STAFF=register msia uni.)

International Business & LAW: ESTATES PER GLYPH HEAD [WHOLE ASIA-GLYPH STACK N SPOILT: BAN]

Fashion Events: LV, CHANEL COCO, Neuromorphic Burberry Bikini

[NEW KLL\$ (2a) Loft Pool Estate diffusion OP: by Phoenix-Lion Tribe ID ATM designer (2b) HORSE DOLLARS LANDED BASIC, ULTRA + FOREST]

PHOENIX \$ LION TRIBE X120 DEBT DUE 1925- 2025 genocide Spoilt land- cannot count	HORSE \$	DRAGON 1: CHAO ZHOU DRAGON- HK MACAU TW LION- (PHOENIX STAR)	DRAGON 2: JP	DRAGON 3: K	PHOENIX GRANITE LANDED ATM: CONTRACTORS SIGN-UP	PHOENIX ROCKET: KEY STATES
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		PORTS RAPISTS: X500 THEFT				
PHOENIX GRANITE LANDED	LANDED	LANDED	LANDED	LANDED	LOGISTICS: PLUG-IN	
PHOENIX LION TRIBE ATM						
TRI- SOLAR ATM	USA CAL 1-2 STATES	CANADA			LOGISTICS: PLUG-IN	

[NEW KLL\$ Loft Pool Estate DIFFUSION OP

+ LANDED basic, ultra, fraud-hdb-bca [no estate, counterfeit] -cpf cash-out + x120 debt PHOENIX ATM DOLLAR BANK
DIFFUSION OP PLUG-IN HORSE ATM: by Phoenix space address: LION TRIBE ID ATM

Add: Dragon 1 Phoenix Chao Zhou ATM [lineage]

Add: Dragon HK ATM [Compute Theft]